

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF Mn(II) AND Cd(II) COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	M.P. (°C)	ΔM (Mhos. cm ²)	%Metal		%Nitrogen	
				Found	Calculated	Found	Calculated
1. MnCl ₂ (DCN) ₂	Light Pink	185	10.8	12.58	12.83	47.68	47.97
2. MnBr ₂ (DCN) ₂	Light Pink	206	8.4	10.45	10.78	40.02	40.30
3. Mn(NCS) ₂ (DCN) ₄	White	192	12.5	11.64	11.71	49.01	49.22
4. Mn(NO ₃) ₂ (DCN) ₄	Light Pink	178	11.8	11.38	11.53	48.22	48.46
5. [Mn(DCN) ₄](ClO ₄) ₂	Light Pink	195	205	9.86	10.07	37.31	37.64
6. CdCl ₂ (DCN) ₂	White	196	6.8	31.71	31.99	31.62	31.87
7. CdBr ₂ (DCN) ₂	White	250	6.4	25.40	25.52	25.15	25.43
8. CdI ₂ (DCN) ₂	White	250	8.7	20.91	21.03	20.78	20.95
9. Cd(NO ₃) ₂ (DCN) ₂	White	190	8.2	27.46	27.79	34.36	34.61
10. Cd(SO ₄) ₂ (DCN) ₂	White	202	11.8	28.06	28.35	35.08	35.32
11. [Cd(DCN) ₄](ClO ₄) ₂	White	205	213	23.12	23.44	46.55	46.72

nature. μ_{eff} values of Mn(II) complexes are ~5.9 B.M indicating a spin-free octahedral or tetrahedral configuration.

Dicyandiamide has the structure I

I.R. spectra of the ligand show several bands in the 3000-3350 cm⁻¹ region attributable to $\nu(\text{N}-\text{H})$. $\delta(\text{NH})$ appears as a weak band at 1660 cm⁻¹. $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ is observed⁹ at 1580 cm⁻¹ and $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ appears at 2170 cm⁻¹. In the complexes there is no splitting or shifting of these characteristic bands excepting $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ which appears around 2220-2260 cm⁻¹ region, suggesting that the ligand is bonded through the nitrile nitrogen atom. Strangely enough though there are four bonding sites, the ligand behaves as monodentate.

In the thiocyanato complexes of Mn(II) and Cd(II) a sharp band is observed at 2090 and 2130 cm⁻¹ due to $\nu(\text{C}\equiv\text{N})$ mode of thiocyanate suggesting⁴ the presence of terminal N-bonded and terminal S-bonded thiocyanato group. In the nitrate complexes ν_4 and ν_1 bands occur at 1400 and 1280 cm⁻¹ region respectively and the difference ($\nabla\nu$) is 120 cm⁻¹ indicating⁵⁻⁷ the presence of monodentate nitrate group. In case of the perchlorate complexes a broad band ~1100 cm⁻¹ suggests⁸⁻¹⁰ the ionic nature of perchlorate group, confirmed by molar conductance data.

Mn(II) complexes show absorption bands ~18.4-18.6, 22.6-22.8, 24.8-25.3 and 27.8 K.K. regions assignable^{11,12} to ν_1 , ν_2 , ν_3 and ν_4 transitions respectively, presumably indicating a high spin octahedral configuration. The perchlorate complex has bands at 20.4, 22.6, 23.8 and 26.6 K.K. regions suggesting^{13,14} a possible tetrahedral geometry. On the basis of analysis, conductance and infrared spectral data cadmium complexes have a tetrahedral configuration.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to U. G. C., New Delhi for financial assistance.

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Separation and Estimation of Aluminium, Titanium and Iron in Bauxite by Paper Electrophoresis

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Manuscript received 14 February 1978, revised 22 August 1978, accepted 9 July 1980

ELECTROPHORETIC technique has been utilised for the quantitative separation of the main constituents of bauxite, as analysis of bauxite can be

achieved with a small amount of bauxite and within a very short time in comparison with the usual standard time consuming and laborious method of separation of bauxite^{1,4}.

Bauxite can be estimated spectrophotometrically after elution of the respective bands for aluminium, titanium and iron from electrophorogram. A drop of bauxite solution of known concentration had been subjected to paper electrophoresis using semimolar lactic acid² as carrier electrolyte. It was found that titanium(IV) moved towards anode, iron(III) and aluminium(III) moved towards cathode after electrophoresis.

Experimental

Preparation of migrant solution :

1.0898 gm of bauxite was decomposed by 10 ml conc. H₂SO₄ and 100 ml of water. After cooling, it was extracted by 100 ml of 6N (1 : 1) HCl and the volume of the solution was made upto 250 ml with 2N H₂SO₄.

Standard method for the analysis of the migrant solution :

Iron was estimated titrimetrically using standard dichromate as usual. Fe(III) and Ti(IV) can be determined together after reduction by passing through the Jone's reductor⁴. The amount of titanium (%) was then obtained by subtracting the amount of iron from the total amount of iron and titanium originally obtained in the volume of the migrant taken. Total quantity of Al₂O₃, Fe₂O₃ and TiO₂ can be determined gravimetrically⁴. The amount (%) of Al₂O₃ was then obtained by subtracting the amount of iron and titanium oxides from the amount of total oxides.

Paper electrophoresis of the migrant and Development of the electrophorogram :

Bauxite solution was electrophorised by using semimolar lactic acid. The zones of the migrants were identified with aqueous chromotropic acid for 'Ti'; alizarin Red-S for 'Al', and potassium ferrocyanide for 'Fe'.

Estimation of Aluminium, Titanium and Iron :

After electrophoresis, the electrophorogram was dried and the portions of the strip containing aluminium, iron and titanium were cut out from the electrophorogram after matching said portions against the stained marked trip.

Aluminium (by Alizarin S) : The region of the strip containing aluminium was taken, eluted with 2N HCl. To the eluted solution, 0.1% alizarin Red-S, ammonium hydroxide and acetic acid were added and the volume made upto the mark with water.

Against the blank solution the optical density of the eluted aluminium solution was measured at the wave length of 510 mμ and found to be 0.026.

Titanium : Portion of the electrophorogram containing titanium was treated with 6N H₂SO₄ and the extraction of titanium ion was made with sulphuric acid, phosphoric acid followed by hydrogen peroxide in the same way as that of aluminium.

Against the blank solution the optical density of the eluted titanium solution was measured at 400 mμ and found to be 0.02.

Iron : The region of the strip containing iron was eluted with 2N hydrochloric acid by the same technique previously followed. To this solution 2M sodium acetate solution was added to bring the pH 3.5 ± 1. To this mixture hydroquinone, acetate buffer, (pH 4.5) and o-phenanthroline were added and the volume made upto the mark with water in 50 ml measuring flask.

Against the blank solution, the optical density of the eluted iron solution was measured after one hour at 510 mμ and found to be 0.03.

Standard solutions potassium of aluminium sulphate KAl(SO₄)₂.12H₂O mol wt 474.7 for aluminium, potassium titanyl oxalate, K₂TiO(C₂O₄)₂.2H₂O for titanium (standardised by standard potassium dichromate after passing through Jone's reductor) and A.R.

TABLE 2

Strength of alum solutions in terms of Al ₂ O ₃ in molarity	O.D.	Strength of potassium titanyl oxalate in terms of TiO ₂ in molarity	O.D.	Strength of ferric ammonium sulphate in terms of iron in molarity	O.D.
6.362 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.024	1.43 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.118	2.15 × 10 ⁻⁵	0.21
7.635 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.029	1.716 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.146	4.62 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.45
9.541 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.035	2.002 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.169	7.12 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.69
12.73 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.048	2.288 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.192	9.72 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.94
17.82 × 10 ⁻⁶	0.068	2.575 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.218	12.4 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.20
		2.860 × 10 ⁻⁴	0.240	14.88 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.45
				17.36 × 10 ⁻⁶	1.69

TABLE 1—DURRUM'S TYPE VERTICAL ELECTROPHORETIC INSTRUMENT³; WHATMAN No 1 PAPER STRIPS (3 cm × 40 cm); POTENTIAL GRADIENT—2.5 volts/cm; CARRIER ELECTROLYTE—SEMIMOLAR LACTIC ACID; TIME OF RUN 5½ HRS; '+', '-' and ':' SIGN INDICATE MIGRATION TOWARDS THE ANODE, THE CATHODE AND THE POINT OF APPLICATION RESPECTIVELY

Migrant	Separation sequences of the migrants and the distance traversed by the zone in cm			
Bauxite	+Ti(IV) : 3 to 2.4	Fe(III) -0.2 to -1.5	Al(III) -5.6 to -10.8	-

TABLE 3

Constituents in Bauxite solution	Optical densities of the eluted solutions after separation by Paper Electrophoresis	Concentrations of the eluted solutions calculated from the different calibration curves	Percentage of the constituents calculated from molar concentrations, volume of migrants, volume of diluents and weight of Bauxite taken	Actual percentage of the constituents calculated by standard methodical analysis
Al ₂ O ₃	0.026	6.9×10^{-6} Molar	53.8%	53.8%
TiO ₂	0.02	0.24×10^{-4} Molar	11%	11.82%
Fe ₂ O ₃	0.03	0.3×10^{-5} Molar	2.575%	2.5%

ferric ammonium sulphate (standardised by standard potassium dichromate) for iron were prepared. By taking different aliquot portions of these solutions calibration curve for aluminium, titanium and iron were drawn from the data as shown in the Table 2.

From the calibration curves of aluminium, titanium and iron the molar concentration of these eluted solutions were calculated and the percentages of Al₂O₃, TiO₂ and Fe₂O₃ in bauxite were calculated as given in the Table 3.

From the table 3, it shows that the technique can be equally utilised for the separation and estimation of aluminium, titanium and iron in bauxite.

Moreover, even with a micro amount of bauxite solution (4.32×10^{-5} gm in 0.01 ml of solution) and within few hours the estimation of the major constituents that is, iron, aluminium and titanium can be done easily without interference when usual standard methods are time consuming, laborious and special cares are to be taken to avoid interference.

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Magneto-Paper Electrophoresis in the Study of Inorganic Ions. Part. II*

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Manuscript received 12 January 1977, accepted 9 July 1980

THE paper describes a comparative study of magnetophoresis, electrophoresis and magneto-electrophoresis with reference to paramagnetic inorganic ions, specially the lanthanide ions. A binodal curve similar to that obtained by plotting μ_{eff} (effective magnetic moments) of the lanthanide (+3) ions at 300°K against atomic number of lanthanons, supports the possible separation of lanthanons by magneto-paper electrophoresis method.

Comparative study :

Successful separation of various inorganic ions by magneto-paper electrophoresis² prompted us to undertake a comparative study of allied techniques¹.

Experimental

An apparatus² with minor modification in order to avoid the hydrostatic flow of the electrolyte, of the following type (Fig. 1) is used.

CIRCUIT DIAGRAM

Fig. 1.

In case of magnetophoresis the key K₁ is disconnected, so that there is no electric-field, whereas in case of electrophoresis the key K₂ is taken out

*Presented at the Pittsburgh Conference on Analytical Chemistry and Applied Spectroscopy, Cleveland, Ohio, U. S. A., 1974. Part I, See H. G. Mukherjee and D. Majumder : *Z. Anal. Chem* 1975, 277, 205.